

Excess thermodynamic parameters for the Pb-Sn alloy at various compositions

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An attempt has been made to evaluate the internal pressure, energy of vaporization and solubility parameter of the Pb-Sn alloy at different temperatures and at various compositions. Excess thermodynamic parameters viz. P_{int}^E and ΔE^E have also been computed for this alloy, and it has been found that it provides useful information about the interaction studies in the undertaken system.

Internal pressure has been a subject of active interest during recent past. It proves to be a useful tool for studying the interaction studies in liquid mixtures. Successful attempts have been made by several investigators¹⁻⁶ to calculate theoretically internal pressure of liquids and liquid mixtures. The role of internal pressure in liquid solution thermodynamics was recognized many years ago by Hildebrand⁷. Pioneering attempts were made by Barton⁸, Rosseinsky⁹, Berkowitz *et al.*¹⁰ and Suryanarayana¹¹ to show the significance of internal pressure as a fundamental property of liquid state and its correlation with other thermodynamic parameters. Hildebrand *et al.*⁷ proposed the concept of cohesive energy density, which is the energy of thermal vaporization from the liquid state to the ideal gas state per unit volume of fluid. The significance of internal pressure and its correlation with solubility parameter (δ) has been discussed by many workers^{3,12,13}. Further, energy of vaporization is the energy required to break all the forces associated with one mole of liquid, during removal of that mole from the liquid to the vapour state. It has also been estimated directly from internal pressure³. Internal pressure of liquid and liquid mixtures can be computed from the experimental values of thermal expansion coefficient (α) and isothermal compressibility (β_T). Suryanarayana⁴ suggested an indirect method for evaluating the internal pressure from the knowledge of viscosity (η), density (ρ) and ultrasonic velocity (u). This approach has been used extensively to study internal pressure of pure liquids, binary liquid mixtures and solutions of electrolytes and non-electrolyte¹³.

An exhaustive survey of literature reveals that several workers^{14,15} estimated the internal pressure of binary liq-

uid mixtures. Margulescu¹⁶ made an attempt to predict internal pressure of pure molten salts, however, such a study for molten alloys are scarcely available. Extensive work has also been carried out on excess thermodynamic properties like excess internal pressure¹⁷ and is still in progress. Pandey and Gupta¹⁸ evaluated the excess internal pressure in binary ionic liquid mixtures. In the present investigation, an attempt has been made to study the variation of internal pressure with temperature and composition in Pb-Sn molten alloy. Energy of vaporization and solubility parameter have also been computed for the alloy at different temperatures. Excess internal pressure and excess energy of vaporization have also been evaluated in order to predict the nature of interactions involved thereof.

Theoretical :

Internal pressure has been computed with the help of the following equation :

$$P_{int} = \alpha \cdot T / \beta_T \quad (1)$$

where all the symbols have their usual notations.

For the binary liquid mixture, the internal pressure has been evaluated by,

$$(P_{int})_{mix} = (\alpha_{mix} \cdot T / \beta_{T mix}) \quad (2)$$

where α_{mix} is the thermal expansion coefficient and $\beta_{T mix}$, the isothermal compressibility of mixture. Also,

$$(P_{int})_{idl} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i (P_{int})_i \quad (3)$$

Here $(P_{int})_{idl}$ is the internal pressure of ideal mixture, x_i , the mole fraction and $(P_{int})_i$, the internal pressure of the

i -th component in a n -component liquid mixture.

For a binary mixture, $(P_{int})_{idl}$ is given by,

$$(P_{int})_{idl} = x_1 (P_{int})_1 + x_2 (P_{int})_2 \quad (4)$$

The excess internal pressure, P_{int}^E , of the binary liquid mixture is given by,

$$P_{int}^E = (P_{int})_{mix} - (P_{int})_{idl}$$

using eqs. (2) and (4), above equation can be expressed as,

$$P_{int}^E = (\alpha_{mix} \cdot T / \beta_{T mix}) - \{x_1 (P_{int})_1 + x_2 (P_{int})_2\} \quad (5)$$

where, $(P_{int})_{mix}$ is the experimental value of internal pressure of mixture and can be evaluated by employing experimental data of α and β_T .

The energy of vaporization, ΔE , is defined as,

$$\Delta E_{mix} = (P_{int})_{mix} \cdot V_m \quad (6)$$

where V_m is the molar volume.

Ideal energy of vaporization is given by,

$$\Delta E_{idl} = (P_{int})_{idl} \cdot V_{idl} \quad (7)$$

where V_{idl} is given by

$$V_{idl} = x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2$$

where V_1 and V_2 are the molar volume of first and second component respectively.

Hence, the excess energy of vaporization can be defined as

$$\Delta E^E = \Delta E_{mix} - \Delta E_{idl} \quad (8)$$

Another useful parameter related with internal pressure is the solubility parameter (δ). It is given by the square root of internal pressure for van der Waals fluids.

$$\delta = \sqrt{P_{int}} \quad (9)$$

Results and discussion

The necessary data needed for the computation of various thermodynamic parameters of Pb-Sn alloy have been taken from the literature¹⁹. Internal pressure, P_{int} , energy of vaporization, ΔE and solubility parameter, δ , have been computed using eqs. (1), (7) and (9) and are recorded in Table 1. Internal pressure, $(P_{int})_{mix}$ and excess internal pressure, P_{int}^E of alloy have been evaluated using eqs. (2) and (5). Energy of vaporization, ΔE_{mix} , excess energy of vaporization, ΔE^E and solubility parameter, δ of alloy have been estimated using eqs. (6) to (9), and are presented in Table-2 at three different temperatures (673, 873 and 973 K) and at

Table 1. Parameters of the pure components

	T	$\alpha \cdot 10^5$	$\beta_T \cdot 10^{12}$	V_m	P_{int}	ΔE	δ
	(K)	(K^{-1})	($cm^2_{int} dyn^{-1}$)	(cm^3)	(Kbar)	(kcal)	(Kbar) ^{1/2}
Pb	673	12.4533	3.650	19.7350	22.962	10.8410	4.7918
	873	12.7670	4.195	20.1441	26.569	12.8038	5.1545
	973	12.8993	4.490	20.4172	27.953	13.6536	5.2870
Sn	673	8.8600	2.788	17.3097	21.451	8.8830	4.6315
	873	8.9986	3.050	17.7079	25.757	10.9115	5.0751
	973	9.0997	3.154	17.8910	28.072	12.0151	5.2983

various compositions.

A perusal of Table 2 reveals that internal pressure increases with increase in temperature. It is also evident from the results that variation of internal pressure with change in composition is not so much marked as is seen the change in case of temperature. The values of internal pressure show

Table 2. Parameters of the Pb-Sn alloy at varying compositions

x_1	T	V_m	P_{int}	P_{int}^E	ΔE	ΔE^E	δ
	(K)	(cm^3)	(Kbar)	(Kbar)	(kcal)	(kcal)	(Kbar) ^{1/2}
0.10	673	17.9716	22.674	1.13	9.749	0.678	4.7617
0.10	873	18.2601	27.925	2.09	12.199	0.207	5.2844
0.10	973	18.4989	29.943	1.89	13.251	0.254	5.4720
0.20	673	18.5657	23.299	1.55	10.348	1.087	4.8269
0.20	873	18.9051	28.016	2.09	12.671	1.389	5.2930
0.20	973	19.0913	30.124	2.07	13.759	1.415	5.4885
0.30	673	19.0804	23.552	1.69	10.751	1.299	4.8530
0.30	873	19.3646	28.270	2.27	13.097	1.628	5.3169
0.30	973	19.7649	30.053	2.01	14.210	1.701	5.4821
0.38	673	19.4623	23.332	1.31	10.863	1.255	4.8303
0.38	873	19.8551	27.789	1.72	13.120	1.499	5.2715
0.38	973	20.0838	29.636	1.61	14.240	1.599	5.4438
0.45	673	19.6461	23.864	1.73	11.216	1.474	4.8851
0.45	873	20.0899	28.184	2.06	13.546	1.795	5.3088
0.45	973	20.3146	30.105	2.08	14.631	1.876	5.4868
0.60	673	19.8644	25.683	3.32	12.205	2.168	5.0678
0.60	873	20.2876	30.258	4.01	14.758	2.722	5.5007
0.60	973	20.5791	32.292	4.29	15.898	2.898	5.6826
0.80	673	19.8432	24.702	2.04	11.726	1.291	4.9701
0.80	873	20.2769	28.849	2.44	13.994	1.536	5.3712
0.80	973	20.5627	30.315	2.33	14.913	1.586	5.5059

an increasing trend at 673 K with increase in the concentration of first component. Although, this trend is not so marked at 873 K, yet an increase is found in the values at 873 K and at 973 K from 10% Pb to 60% Pb, and then again a decrease in the values at 80% Pb, at these temperatures.

Excess internal pressure of the Pb-Sn alloy also increases as temperature increases. The increase in $P_{\text{int}}^{\text{E}}$ is quite evident when temperature is raised from 673 to 873 K, whereas it is not that much evident on raising the temperature from 873 to 973 K. However, at some places the values of $P_{\text{int}}^{\text{E}}$ decrease, viz. at 973 K for 10% Pb, at 973 K for 30% Pb, at 973 K for 38% Pb and at 973 K for 80% Pb. These discrepancies have been attributed to the fact that at these places, interactions between the components of the alloy are much more prevalent at higher temperature say at 973 K. A careful observation shows that in the temperature range 673 to 973 K interactions are weak because of magnitude and positive sign of excess internal pressure.

Internal pressure is directly related with the energy of vaporization and solubility parameter. The values of solubility parameter are found to range from $4.7617 \text{ (Kbar)}^{1/2}$ to $5.0678 \text{ (Kbar)}^{1/2}$ at 673 K; $5.2715 \text{ (Kbar)}^{1/2}$ to $5.5007 \text{ (Kbar)}^{1/2}$ at 873 K and $5.4438 \text{ (Kbar)}^{1/2}$ to $5.6826 \text{ (Kbar)}^{1/2}$ at 973 K. Amongst these, the values are found to be the highest when the alloy contains 60% Pb. So, we can conclude that the sign and magnitude of computed excess thermodynamic parameters indicate weak interactions in Pb-Sn alloy.

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References

1. D. O. Macdonald and J. B. Hyne, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1971, **49**, 611, 2336; 1976, **54**, 2813.
2. J. H. Hildebrand and R. L. Scott, "Regular Solutions", Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, USA, 1962.
3. M. R. J. Dack, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 1643; *J. Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1975, **4**, 211.
4. C. V. Subrahmanyam, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1989, **27**, 751.
5. J. D. Pandey, N. Tripathi and R. Dey, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1996, **70 B**, 147.
6. J. D. Pandey, G. P. Dubey, N. Tripathi and A. K. Singh, *J. Int. Acad. Phys. Sci.*, 1997, **1**, 117.
7. J. H. Hildebrand and R. L. Scott, "Solubility of Non-Electrolytes", Reinhold, New York, 1964.
8. A. F. M. Barton, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1971, **48**, 156.
9. D. R. Rosseinsky, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **81**, 1578.
10. N. Berkowitz and S. C. Srivastava, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **41**, 1787.
11. C. V. Suryanarayana, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, 1977, **4**, 111.
12. J. A. R. Renuncio, G. J. F. Breedveld and J. M. Prausnitz, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **4**, 81.
13. L. Ines Acevedo, C. Pedrosa and M. Katz, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1990, **19**, 11.
14. S. V. Subrahmanyam, K. Malakondiah and V. Hyderkhan, *Acustica*, 1980, **45**, 196.
15. S. V. Subrahmanyam, T. Rarnajappa and E. Rajagopal, *Acustica*, 1981, **49**, 261.
16. I. G. Margulescu, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1969, **14**, 963.
17. J. D. Pandey and Ranjan Dey, *Acoustics Lett.*, 2000, **24**, 105.
18. J. D. Pandey and U. Gupta, *Z. Phys. Chemie (Leipzig)*, 1987, **268**, 477.
19. G. V. Konyudnenb, *High Temp (USA)*, 1972, **10**, 272; *Translation of Teplopic Vrs Temp (USSR)*, 1972, **10**, 309.